

HF and MP2 calculations on two Schiff base ligands and stability constant studies on some of their metal complexes

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Abstract : HF and MP2 studies were carried out for Schiff bases of furfural with L-glutamic acid (glu) and L-aspartic acid (asp). The Schiff bases are non-planar and the probable binding sites are furan oxygen, imino nitrogen and α - and γ -carboxylato oxygens. The HF stability enhancement due to the formation of Schiff bases furfural-glu and furfural-asp is respectively 19.45 and 18.07 kcal/mol. With these Schiff base ligands, Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} form $\text{M}(\text{AB})$, MAB_2 and $\text{M}(\text{AB})_2$ complexes and Cu^{II} forms MAB species. The furfural-glu binds the metal ions in tridentate manner through furan and α -carboxylato oxygens and imino nitrogen. The furfural-asp is tetradentate and binds the metal ions through furan oxygen, imino nitrogen and carboxylato oxygens in MAB species. However, it is tridentate in MAB_2 and $\text{M}(\text{AB})_2$ complexes.

Keywords : Computation, furfural, amino acid, potentiometry.

The study of Schiff bases has gained interest due to their potential applications^{1,2}. Schiff bases with an additional donor atom closer to the imino nitrogen are capable to form cavity of various size and this can accommodate metal ions³. There are many experimental and theoretical reports on Schiff bases⁴⁻⁸. Schiff bases of furfural have medicinal activities and are used as antifungal and antitumor agents⁵⁻⁹. The present paper reports the computation and equilibrium studies on Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} -furfural (A)-L-glutamic acid (glu) and L-aspartic acid (asp) (B) Schiff base complex systems.

Results and discussion

Theoretical studies on the binding tendency of the Schiff base ligands :

The structure of the Schiff base ligands is given in Fig. 1. Important geometrical parameters are given in Table 1. Dihedral $\text{C}_4\text{-C}_5\text{-C}_6\text{-N}_7$ for the two Schiff base ligands is around 166° . This indicates that furan oxygen and imino nitrogen atoms are distorted from planarity. The torsion twist between furan ring and imino nitrogen is $\sim 14^\circ$. This distortion is mainly due to the repulsive force generated between furan oxygen and imino nitrogen. The charges on the O_{11} and N_7 for the Schiff bases are increased and decreased respectively than that of the corresponding amino acids. The enhanced stability due to the formation of Schiff bases from furfural and glu and asp by HF method

is respectively 19.45 and 18.07 kcal/mol. Based on Milliken charge density the binding ability of donor atoms (Table 1) in furfural-glu is in the order : α -carboxylato oxygen > γ -carboxylato oxygen > furan oxygen > imino nitrogen. In furfural-asp system, the γ -carboxylato oxygen is replaced by β -carboxylato oxygen. The Schiff bases are potentially tetradentate and they can bind the metal ion through α - and γ -carboxylato oxygens, furan oxygen and imino nitrogen.

Solution studies :

In addition to various binary species, in the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} -furfural (A)-glu and asp (B) systems MAB , MAB_2 and $\text{M}(\text{AB})_2$ complexes were detected, while in the Cu^{II} systems only MAB complex was found to be present.

Stability and structure of MAB species : The preferential formation of the ternary complex species over binary species can be illustrated by considering the stepwise formation constants of the various species formed, e.g. in the Co^{II} -furfural (A)-glu (B) system the Scheme 1 clearly indicates the preferential formation of the ternary species over that of the binary complexes. If MAB species are mixed ligand complexes, their overall formation constant values are 6.56, 7.67, 10.47 and 6.72 log units ($1/2 \log K_{20} + 1/2 \log K_{02} + 0.3010$) respectively for Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} -furfural (A)-glu (B) systems. But the $\log \beta_{\text{MAB}}$ values for M^{II} -furfural (A)-glu (B) ($\text{M} =$

Table 1. Important parameters of furfural-glu and -asp Schiff bases

Schiff base	RHF/6-31G*						MP2/6-31G*					
	Dihedral (°)		Charge (-)				Dihedral (°)		Charge (-)			
	C ₄ -C ₅ - C ₆ -N ₇	N ₇ -C ₈ - C ₉ -O ₁₁	O ₁	N ₇	O ₁₁	β-/γ- Carboxylato oxygen	C ₄ -C ₅ - C ₆ -N ₇	N ₇ -C ₈ - C ₉ -O ₁₁	O ₁	N ₇	O ₁₁	β-/γ- Carboxylato oxygen
fur-glu	166.0756	-78.4200	0.6258	0.4847	0.7329	0.7025	166.9000	-80.6026	0.6465	0.4950	0.7520	0.7153
fur-asp	170.6620	-80.2571	0.6341	0.5436	0.7295	0.7117	168.8899	-82.2779	0.6555	0.5700	0.7473	0.7362

Scheme 1. Stepwise formation of various species of Co^{II}-furfural (A)-glu (B) system : (A) furfural, (B) glue, (AB) Schiff base.

Co, Ni, Cu and Zn) are 10.56, 12.23, 17.51 and 10.58 respectively. The higher experimental values indicate the presence of strong inter-ligand interaction between the -CHO group of furfural (A) and the amino group of the ligand, B. Thus all are Schiff base complexes. At a first glance, the above experimental values compare favorably with the values obtained in the corresponding M^{II}-furfural (A)-val (B) systems¹⁰. This shows that the Schiff base in M^{II}-furfural-glu functions as tridentate through furan oxygen, imino nitrogen and α-carboxylato oxygen atoms.

The stability constant values for M^{II}-furfural (A)-asp (B) (M = Co, Ni, Cu and Zn) are 10.94, 13.08, 18.26 and 11.20 respectively. These values are ~1 log units higher than those in the corresponding M^{II}-furfural-val system¹⁰. Therefore, the Schiff base (AB) in the MAB species of M^{II}-furfural-asp can bind in tetradentate mode via furan oxygen, imino nitrogen and two carboxylato oxygen groups. This would result in the formation of two five and one six membered rings. The formation of the multi-ring system will naturally enhance the stability of the complex.

The species distribution diagram further conform the preferential formation of ternary Schiff base species over the binary species. For Co^{II} system, CoAB is predominantly present in the pH range of 6.5 to 7.5 with the maximum of 73% and 52% of the total metal ion concentration respectively for Co^{II}-furfural-glu and -asp systems. Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} systems follow the similar trend. In the case of Cu^{II} systems CuAB species predominant in the pH range of 5.5–7.6 and reaches a maximum of 75%.

Stability and structure of MAB₂ species : The log β_{MAB₂}

values are respectively 14.63, 16.41 and 14.84 in Co, Ni and Zn-furfural-glu systems. These higher values indicate the formation of Schiff base complexes. When compared to the similar species of fural-val¹⁰, the above values are ~0.6 log units higher. This enhancement is not enough to generate an additional donor site in glu compared to val. Further, the log K value for the formation of Co(AB)B from CoAB is higher than the log K_{MB}^{MB} value by ~0.7 units. This enhancement in the stability constant value may be due to the interaction between γ-carboxylato group and metal ion of the neighboring complex¹¹. This leads to the conclusion that the Schiff base (AB) in M(AB)B is tridentate similar to the binding of (AB) in M(AB) and the second glu binds independently the metal.

The log β_{MAB₂} values in M^{II}-furfural (A)-asp (B) systems are 15.26, 18.42 and 15.59 units respectively for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} systems. This higher value implies that it is a mixed ligand complex of the type M(AB)B. Further its stability constant value is ~1 log units higher than the corresponding species of fural-val¹⁰ system. This may be accounted by considering the tetradentate binding of Schiff base in the furfural-asp system. The second asp can bind independently. The M(AB)B species was found formed above pH 7.3 and reaches the maximum of 25% of the total metal ion.

Stability and structure of MA₂B₂ species : The log log β_{MA₂B₂} values for M^{II}-furfural-glu systems (M = Co, Ni and Zn) are 16.73, 18.79 and 16.94 respectively. This is

Fig. 1. Structure of ligand furfural (A)-glu and -asp (B) : R = -(CH₂)₂COOH, -CH₂COOH.

comparable with similar species of M^{II} -furfural-val system¹⁰. Therefore, the tridentate binding of both the Schiff base (AB) ligand in $M(AB)_2$ complex can be expected.

The $\log \beta_{MA_2B_2}$ values observed for the $M(AB)_2$ complex in the M^{II} -furfural-asp systems are 17.19, 20.43 and 17.58 respectively for Co, Ni and Zn. Here also, both the Schiff base ligands coordinate tridentately through the furan oxygen, imino nitrogen and carboxylato oxygen present in the β -position to the imino nitrogen. The $M(AB)_2$ species is predominant in 1 : 2 systems. In 1 : 1 systems it is formed after pH 7.3 and reaches a maximum of 35%. While in 1 : 2 systems it was formed after pH 7.0 and reached a maximum of 70% of total metal ion.

Experimental

HF and MP2 calculations were carried out using GAMESS program¹¹. 6-31G* basis set¹² was used in this calculations. The entire chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Metals were taken in the form of nitrates. Furfural, glu and asp were obtained from Sigma. The stability constants were studied potentiometrically at 25 °C at $I = 0.1 \mu$ by batch wise titration method¹³. The Schiff base equilibria were studied by method describes earlier¹⁰. The formation constants for the Schiff base complexes were calculated using computer programme¹³ designed for evaluation of Schiff base complex equilibria. The supporting data related to the binary complexes under the present experimental conditions needed for the computation of Schiff base complex equilibria were taken from the literature¹⁴.

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